

Digital Resilience: Assessing Potential Post-Pandemic Business Opportunities and the Impact of Digital Marketing Strategies

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Abstract: The COVID-19 situation has impacted adversely many business organisations, from small-scale businesses to large-scale businesses/ or multinational corporations, leading to decline in revenues and subsequent losses. On the contrary, there are other new age digital businesses who have thrived even in this situation as they were better prepared both technologically as well as from the point of view of mindset and attitude. As such, there is a clear advantage that can be seen between the digital and non-digital. The purpose of this study is to find out various digital opportunities, digital skillsets required by the existing and upcoming digital entrepreneurs. This study has adopted a Quantitative research methodology, followed by primary data collection with 120 anonymous respondents. The primary data has been analysed further using various advanced scientific tools like IBM SPSS, Microsoft Power BI, giving valuable insights on the digital business opportunities. The digital business, digital skillsets like digital marketing has a great deal of awareness amongst the entrepreneurs and professional group of Urban Indian cities. The Indian participants are aware about digital businesses opportunities and digital marketing skillset. It should be highlighted that, overall, there is a great deal of awareness about the performances of the digital businesses and digital skills particularly digital marketing based on different methods of statistical analysis as conducted, it is important especially for the small and medium businesses in India to capitalize on this positive sentiment and mindset on digital eco-system where there is a great deal of optimism for future business in India as reflected in the research study.

Keywords: Digital Business; Digital Marketing; Digital Skillsets; Digital Entrepreneurs; COVID-19; Digital

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1. Introduction

The year 2020 will clearly go down as the ‘black-swan’ moment in the recent history of humankind. The COVID-19 situation has adversely impacted many business organisations, leading to a decline in revenues or losses. On the contrary, there are new age digital businesses which performed exceptionally well in 2020 like, Amazon with 65% profit growth (Amazon quarterly results, 2020), Alphabet with 55% profit growth (Alphabet quarterly results, 2020) and Facebook with 12% profit growth (Facebook quarterly results, 2020). Further, digital revenue of US retailers grew by 68% by April 2020, with US & Canada e-commerce orders having over 129% growth on a year-on-year basis Columbus (2020). US e-commerce sales is forecasted at US\$709.78 billion in 2020, highest jump in one year, and global e-commerce sales forecasted at US\$4.2 trillion by end 2020 Wertz (2020). E-commerce sector in India also grew by 17% post COVID-19 Makhija (2020).

Taking cue from the above growth of digital businesses, the aim of this research study is to evaluate the potential digital business opportunities and ascertain the importance of digital skillsets, primarily, digital marketing in driving the digital businesses, post COVID-19.

1.1. Problem Statement

Digital businesses are growing exponentially globally, and many digital start-ups and new age entrepreneurs have tasted success. However, there are problems being faced by many traditional business owners across Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) who are not using this massive opportunity to the optimum because of various reasons, such as, lack of funds, lack of knowledge and skill sets, or unawareness of the opportunities that a digital business can provide. This research study is focussed around addressing this problem with a solution to encourage potential entrepreneurs and new age businesses to leverage the opportunity provided by the digital businesses.

1.2. Research questions

With the problems that there is not adequate awareness of the digital business opportunities available and the importance of digital skillsets, especially digital marketing, below research questions were framed:

1. What are the digital business opportunities available?
2. What are the new digital skillsets required?
3. Is there an understanding on the importance of digital marketing and what are the key digital marketing strategies?
4. What are the suggestions on strategies for Digital Businesses?

1.3. Research aim and objectives

From the above research questions the aim of the research study was arrived at which was to evaluate the potential digital business opportunities post COVID-19 and analyse the new skillsets and the role of digital marketing in digital businesses. Objectives of this research study were framed taking in consideration the research questions and aim. The objectives that were ascertained at the start of the project for the new age entrepreneurs, traditional businesses, and professionals, were the following:

- To examine the new digital business opportunities that are available
- To analyse the new digital skillsets required
- To determine the importance of digital marketing and recommend key digital marketing strategies and solutions
- To suggest various strategies for Digital Businesses.

1.4. Hypotheses

This research study had following null hypotheses for each objective, which have been tested in the findings section.

Objective 1: To examine the new digital business opportunities that are available

H_0 = There is no difference in the importance given to the business performance of digital businesses

H_0 = There is no willingness to establish a digital start-up

H_0 = There is no relationship between digital opportunity or strength and preference given by both digital and non-digital professionals

Objective 2: To analyse the new digital skillsets required

H_0 = There is no difference in preference (in ranking) for digital skillsets across age groups

Objective 3: To determine the importance of digital marketing and recommend key digital marketing strategies and solutions

H_0 = There is no awareness on the level of importance of digital marketing strategies across segments.

H_0 = There is no willingness to give priority to Digital Marketing as a skillset

Objective 4: To suggest various strategies for Digital Businesses

H_0 = There is no correlation amongst Digital Business growth, Digital Marketing and Digital start-up

2. Literature Review

New digital business opportunities available

There is plethora of research work available on the new digital opportunities available post COVID-19 as the world has moved towards Digital. Study was conducted on growth in technology and online platforms during COVID-19 in India Kaur et al. (2020). This study of 221 Indian participants examined the extent of usage of technology and digital platforms post COVID-19 and indicated that with people staying at home there was increased demand for digital tracking apps, digital payments, online education, online entertainment, and communication portals like zoom, webex, teams and it was concluded that future growth is predicted in these arenas. Supporting the study of digital interaction, Oranburg and Tamasy (2020), analysed the change in teaching methodology from offline to online and examined strengths and weaknesses of various teaching methods and made suggestion for the hybrid teaching method which is more digital focussed. Change in work styles has led to increased use of online collaboration tools eg. zoom, teams, slack etc was also highlighted Kodama (2020). However, with the change in work styles focus on cybersecurity is the need of the hour Babbs (2020). Further, with reference to Indo pacific region, there is a growing need for digital transformation/ digital infrastructure Runde et al. (2020) which was also supported by Bachhawat et al. (2020) the technology co-operation between India and Australia in the fields of Artificial Intelligence (AI), quantum/space technologies amongst others, which will give a boost to the industries. K and M (2020) highlighted the increased innovations and digital transformation in various sectors. Gore (2020) supported this with his findings on the digital innovations/ entrepreneurship in India post COVID-19.

Digitalisation in Asia was associated with growth in business transformations, technological innovations, digital entrepreneurship Li et al. (2020). Increased digitalisation in various sectors in India was highlighted namely in education, pharma, financial, retail, manufacturing Perumal and Chitra (2020) with growth in associated opportunities Badam and Gochhait (2020) and Pant and Shende et al. (2020) and Singh et al. (2019). Further, various opportunities were highlighted from digital marketing through social media marketing (SMM), use of AI, augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) technologies Dwivedi et al. (2020). Though, AI comes with its own threats which needs to be addressed Coombs (2020). Rising consumer demand for online shopping from all parts of India (urban as well as rural) and social media platforms was also highlighted in E-commerce Trends Report Makhija (2020). Data governance, privacy and security was highlighted as a key concern De, Pandey and Pal (2020) and Singh et al. (2019) and Dwivedi et al. (2020) and Fahey and Hino et al. (2020) which implied that there are opportunities in this field.

New skill sets required

With respect to digital skillsets, Giriraj (2017) examined the growth of digital marketing in India and analysed published literature over a period of five years and found that many marketing professionals are resorting to digital marketing with the increased use of mobile phones and e-commerce platforms. The study concluded that digital marketing is extremely crucial for businesses as well as the consumers in near future. Digital marketing capabilities gap Herhausen et al. (2020) was examined by mix of interview and survey responses of 169 managers which found two gaps, practice gap - signifying difference between current practices and the ideal digital marketing capability and, knowledge gap - signifying gap in knowledge. The study concluded that there is a digital marketing skillset gap and businesses should close this gap as digital sales are on a surge. Chatterjee and Kar (2020) went further to analyse the factors that would help SMEs in India to adopt social media marketing (SMM), in their digital marketing strategy, and impact of SMM on business performance. This study of 310 random entrepreneurs in India was examined to assess what factors motivate SME to use SMM and found that there are various factors (perceived use, competency, cost) which motivate the SMEs to use SMM and that there is positive impact on business performance of the SMEs through SMM. The study concluded that SMM leads to enhanced growth and better customer engagement. However, there is a competency gap which needs to be corrected through trainings.

Dwivedi et al. (2020) supported this and further analysed various opportunities through SMM, AI, AR/VR technologies. The study examined insights from leading experts in the field of digital marketing and SMM. The study concluded that there are immense opportunities to increase the business performance through enhanced customer engagement by use of various digital marketing tools (SMM, AI, AR/VR), however, businesses should carefully manage the related issues (ethics, trust, transparency) with the data sharing. Dwivedi et al. (2020) also emphasised on the advancement in digital marketing activities like display advertising, search engine marketing, SMM and mobile marketing amongst others. Interestingly, Melović et.al. (2020) also found that digital marketing resulted in better brand positioning, promotion and increase in brand awareness.

Key digital marketing strategies and solutions

Going a step further on the digital marketing strategy, Garg, et al. (2020) studied the relationship between social media analytics, business performance and customer engagement in the Indian retail and information technology industry. This study of 281 digital marketing executives examined the impact of social media analytics on customer engagement and business performance and found that there is a positive relationship between them concluding that through social media analytic an organisation can increase its

business performance through better customer engagement. Similarly, Juntunen, et al. (2020), studied the impact of B2B user engagement in social media content and how big companies used digital marketing social media content strategies, objectives, and tactics on Twitter. This analysis of top 20 global B2B brands' twitter account over a period of two years (6900+ tweets) found that a variety of objectives, strategies and tactics are used by companies to create awareness, trust, knowledge, liking and interest amongst users to get more user engagement. Focus on social media strategy in business-to-business marketing was also supported by Kumar et al. (2020). Marchand et.al. (2020) also recommended social media resources and capabilities, as a digital marketing tool, to enhance social media performance and brand perceptions.

Another study by Saura (2020) analysed the methods, uses and performance metrics of data science in the digital marketing strategy. The study provided various concepts, methods, performance metrics and models which can be used to gather insights from large amount of data and concluded that data science can be used efficiently for determining a robust digital marketing strategy. Personalised digital marketing strategy was the focus of Behra et al. (2020) who proposed a model for personalised digital marketing by providing personalised marketing content to the consumers. The model was tested on random sampling of 100 customers of a mid-size healthcare retailer in India and found positive impacts in the revenue growth for the business. The study concluded that personalised recommendation engine as a digital marketing strategy brings in higher revenue for the business and at the same time also saves consumers time by making recommendations based on their buying patterns. With digital marketing and social media, it is important to follow ethical practices while using publicly available social media information Jacobson et al. (2020).

Key digital business strategies

There are many recommendations on digital business strategies for businesses. Sestino et al. (2020) analysed the reshaping of business functions with IoT and Big Data and focussed on the implementation of digital transformation as a strategy to exploit IoT and Big Data for better business performance. The study was conducted through review of literature over last 10 years in IoT and Big Data and concluded that business transformation strategy using IoT and Big Data can impact the businesses positively. In another study relating to digital platforms, Raj et al. (2020) analysed how digital platforms affected restaurant business during COVID-19, examined data from Uber eats for small and medium restaurants across US cities and found an increasing trend of people ordering food through digital platform. The study highlighted the importance of digital platforms and the shift towards digital interaction as a business strategy. Similarly, Papadopoulos et al. (2020) highlighted the increased use of digital technologies as a strategy by SMEs.

Pellegrini et al. (2020) supported the importance of online education and stressed on strategy of reimagining and redesigning the higher education arena with digital teaching. Similarly, De Filippo et al. (2020) found increased digitalisation in Italian education; digital transformation of basic education was also examined by Iivari et al. (2020). Pant and Shende (2020) analysed the impact of COVID-19 on the ever-growing sharing economy in India comprised of the likes of Uber, Zomato, Airbnb and WeWork. This study was conducted using company and industry reports, complimented with stakeholders' interviews, and concluded that increased digitalisation strategy would present an opportunity for the businesses to revive and achieve profits. Similarly and Khan (2020) supported the digitalisation strategy by analysing the FDI inflows into India and concluded that companies should focus on enhancing technology capability development, IoT, AR/VR and the like which will provide growth opportunities. Going further, Seetharaman (2020) analysed the impact on business models due to COVID-19. The study analysed various industries using information intensity matrix framework to examine the shift in the firm's strategy and found that there are many firms who changed their strategy and business model to adapt to the COVID-19 scenario and there was a surge in usage of digital products/ services. Supporting diversified business models, Aversa, P. et al. (2020) analysed Amazon's diversified but integrated business model and stressed the importance of an integrated digital business model for better competitive advantage and business growth.

2.1. Research Gap

The above research reviews were very insightful; however, the above studies have a gap in addressing all the aspects together namely new digital opportunities, digital skillsets requirement, digital marketing strategies and strategies for digital business in one cohesive study. Further, most of the research analysis are carried out pre-COVID period. Hence, while these are relevant, the current environment is very dynamic, and things have changed since many countries experienced a second wave of COVID-19. With the above literature review in consideration, it is important that new research on this topic be done, which would give a fresh perspective and is more recent and binds all the research areas into one.

2.2. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this research study has been explained in Figure 1 below, it explains that the goal of this research study was to evaluate the potential digital business opportunities, post COVID-19 and to analyse the significance of the role digital marketing plays in digital businesses and ascertain the awareness of both these aspects.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

The framework summarises the objectives of this research study and explains that the objectives can be fulfilled with the study of digital businesses and digital marketing by conducting the market research.

3. Research Methodology

Realism philosophy has been followed in the present research. This research philosophy has contributed immensely to the findings of the potential digital business opportunities and the important role played by digital marketing post COVID-19. Mono method has been followed in this research study as this research has followed only the quantitative method based on primary data as well as secondary data. The online survey had a total of 158 anonymous participants who chose to respond to the survey, 120 from the above had completed their survey, same has been used for the quantitative analysis in this report. A sample size of 120 was used to get statistical output clearing the Validity and Reliability tests for various analysis. The respondents of the questionnaires were public belonging primarily to urban cities of India, current or potential entrepreneurs or job professionals as reflected in the profile captured in the response sheets. The online survey was anonymous.

The sampling technique of online method is convenient technique. Questionnaires were posted on the social media sites like LinkedIn, Facebook using the questionnaire links and QR codes. Furthermore, the cross-sectional analysis was used for this research work.

3.1. Validity and Reliability

The content validity was conducted for the designing of the questionnaires by ensuring that feedback was taken from 7 digital business consultants and owners. The construct validity was ensured by taking feedback from statistical data experts on variables and different types of statistical measures like ordinal, scale and nominal data while keeping the research objective as the key focus.

Table 1: Reliability Test – Cronbach’s Alpha

Questionnaire Data Testing for Reliability – Cronbach’s Alpha	Cronbach’s Alpha	Cronbach’s Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
Combination Digital Marketing, Digital Business and Digital skillsets for future	0.906	0.906	18
Business which performed well	0.869	0.869	9
Digital Business – Future Growth	0.863	0.863	9
Threats and Opportunities to Business	0.823	0.824	18
Business Challenges and Performances Questionnaires	0.843	0.843	10
Lack of which skilled to loss or reduction of Income	0.787	0.797	8
Skills set that helped to reduce loss	0.818	0.850	8

Source : Created on IBM SPSS especially for this Research Study

In the context of reliability, the research study has been conducted giving much importance to the critical factors for the research analysis while working with data, Bell et al., (2019) find Cronbach’s alpha figure of 0.8 to be at an acceptable level, however, also acknowledged acceptability of 0.7 “as a rule of thumb” where 0.7 is “considered to be efficient” .Schutte et al. (2000), as cited in Bell et al., (2019). For this research study all data cleared the reliability test and the reliability test in some cases were as high as 0.906 (Refer Table 1). As such, reliability test has been given importance while conducting this research analysis.

4. Findings

The findings for this research work have been done, primarily, by using the Mono method using quantitative analysis, Primary data has been used using the instrument of questionnaire with responses from 120 participants. The analysis has been conducted using some of the most advanced statistical tools like IBM SPSS, and supported by Microsoft power BI, the methods and processes that have been used for the analysis are descriptive

statistical findings, spearman's correlation, Paired sample T test, Mann Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha and validate test with the help of statisticians. The collected data of 120 participants were used to analyse the findings using various methods, the data was collected using the instrument of online questionnaire attracting participants primarily from the urban cities of India using social media, following are the demographic findings.

4.1. Demographic profile of the respondents

The total number of valid respondents are 120, 52% of the respondents are Male and 48% of the respondents are Female. The age group of the respondents and the subsequent mix are in the categories of 18-30 years are 23%, 31-45 years are 28%, 46-60 years are 30% and 61 and above years are 18%. The marital status of the participants has a mix of 39% Single and 61% Married. The respondents have reasonably good level of education with 47% having masters' degree or PHD and 53% have Bachelors 'degree or below. The data also has an interesting mix of Digital and Non-digital professionals 44% of the participants are from the Digital professional or business background, whereas the remaining 56% are from Non-Digital backgrounds. 47% of them are salaried, 32% of them are entrepreneurs, rest 21% of them are into other different professions. The survey also includes the data on the post COVID-19 impact on the income of the participants – 26% have maintained status quo, neither increase no decrease in their income. 32% of them were able to increase their income post COVID-19 and rest 42% experienced decline in their monthly income or profits, post COVID-19.

Objective 1: To examine the new digital business opportunities that are available

Objective 1: Null Hypotheses 1

The following is the null hypothesis that has been tested, using Mann Whitney U Test, which is a comparison of the means of the ranked data of the questionnaire.

H_0 = There is no difference in the importance given to the business performance of digital businesses

H_1 = There is a difference in the importance given to the business performance of digital businesses (Alternate)

If we look Table 2, we find that for the ranking given by the Digital and the non-digital professionals, the significance value is greater than 0.05 in all the 5 above cases. This has meant that the null hypotheses cannot be rejected and as such, has been accepted in all the cases. As such we can infer that there is no significant difference in the mean of ranking between the two groups in all the above cases. The findings from the above analysis are that

all the participants – all of whom consist of digital as well as the non-digital professionals. They are all overly optimistic about the digital business’s future opportunities.

Table 2: Mann-Whitney U Test – Mean Rank between Digital & non-Digital

Summary of Mann-Whitney U Tests Mean Rank of Digital or Non-Digital	Non-Digital Professional	Digital Professional	p-value Asymp.Sig. (2-tailed)	Null-Hypotheses
Rank, which businesses performed well				
Digital Marketing Services	59.57	61.75	0.728	Accepted
Digital Business	64.23	55.45	0.154	Accepted
AI & Robotics	61.46	59.21	0.720	Accepted
Traditional Non-Digital Business	60.31	60.75	0.944	Accepted
E-Commerce	61.88	58.64	0.610	Accepted

N=69 (Non-Digital Professional / Business Owner)

N = 51 (Digital Professional / Business Owner)

Source : Created on IBM SPSS especially for this Research Study

Objective 1: Null Hypotheses 2

The following is the null hypothesis that has been tested, using paired sample T Test, which is a comparison of two Ordinal questionnaire based on rating.

H_0 = There is no willingness to establish a digital start-up

H_1 = There is a willingness to establish a digital start-up (Alternate)

In Table 3, the significance value is less than 0.05 and thus, the mean of digital start-up at 2.32 is significantly higher than 2.21. Hence, the null hypotheses stand rejected. So, the alternate hypotheses H_1 stated above stands true. The finding from this analysis is that there is a significantly higher preference to establish a digital start-up that to join or continue a digital business which is profitable.

Table 3: Paired Sample T Test 1 – Mean of Digital Start-up willingness & Digital growth%

Summary of Paired Sample T Test 1 Testing the relationship between two ordinal questions	Mean-Digital Startup willingness	MEAN – Rating on profitability growth % of Digital Business post COVID – 19	p-value Asymp.Sig. (2-tailed)	Null Hypotheses
Paired sample T Test between the Group of Rating on Profitability growth % of Digital Business vs Rating Group willingness for a Digital Startup post COVID-19	2.32	2.21	0.032	Rejected

N=120 (Total successful respondents) Normality test passed with p-value > 0.05 Source : Created on IBM SPSS especially for this Research Study

Objective 1: Null Hypotheses 3

Table 4: Chi-Square Test– Relationship between Business Opportunity and Digital/Non-digital professional groups

Chi-square Test	What is your Profession							
Summary of Chi-square Test Testing the relationship between questions / variables	Non-Digital professional		Digital Professional		Digital + Non- Digital Professional		P-value	Null hypotheses
Questionnaires Biggest Business Opportunity post COVID – 19'								
AI & Robotics	13	56	19	32	32	88	0.024	Rejected
E-Commerce	23	46	30	21	53	67	0.005	Rejected
Digital Services – Consultancy, Banking	47	22	43	8	90	30	0.043	Rejected
Tele communication	23	46	2	49	25	95	< 0.001	Rejected
Traditional Business	15	54	1	50	16	104	0.002	Rejected

N=69 (Non-Digital Professional / Business Owner)

N = 51 (Digital Professional / Business Owner)

Source : Created on IBM SPSS especially for this Research Study

The following is the null hypothesis that has been tested, using the Chi-square Method findings of relationship between a category split of Digital and non-digital Professionals and the responses that they have given in the form of Yes and No in these multiple questionnaires, as follows:

H_0 = There is no relationship between digital opportunity or strength and preference given by both digital and non-digital professionals

H_1 = There is a relationship between digital opportunity or strength and preference given by both digital and non-digital professionals (Alternate)

In the Table 4, it is quite clear that the significance value is less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$) in all the cases as mentioned in the Chi-Square table, as such the null hypotheses stands rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the digital and non-digital professionals and the biggest digital business opportunity questionnaire. Thus, digital professionals are the ones who are relatively more optimistic about the digital business opportunity compared to non-digital business professionals. Thus, the alternate hypotheses H_1 , stated above stands true.

Objective 2: To analyse the new digital skillsets required

Objective 2: Null Hypothesis 1

The following is the null hypothesis that has been tested, using Mann Whitney U Test, which is a comparison of the means of the ranked data of the questionnaire:

H_0 = There is no difference in preference (in ranking) for digital skillsets across age groups

H_1 = There is difference in preference (in ranking) for digital skillsets across age groups (Alternate)

Table 5: Mann-Whitney U Test – Mean Rank between Younger and Older group

Summary of Mann-Whitney U Tests Mean Rank by Younger or Older group	18-45 Years Younger Age group	45 + years Older age group	p-value Asymp.Sig. (2 tailed)	Null – hypotheses
Rank, which skillset you would improve post COVID19				
Digital Business	59.76	61.29	0.805	Accepted
Social Media Skills	63.69	57.09	0.291	Accepted
Programming or Coding	64.87	55.83	0.146	Accepted
AI & Robotics	59.36	61.72	0.702	Accepted
Digital Marketing	65.79	54.84	0.067	Accepted

N=62 (18-45 Years Younger Age Group)

N = 58 (45 + years Older Age Group)

Source : Created on IBM SPSS especially for this Research Study

In Table 5, it is evident that p-value in all the 5 cases is greater than the statistically significant 0.05, as such the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Hence, accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the mean ranking given between the two groups – younger and older. As such, we can interpret that there is awareness amongst both the groups about these skillsets are important for their future.

Objective 3: To determine the importance of digital marketing and recommend key digital marketing strategies and solutions.

Objective 3: Null Hypothesis 1

The following is the null hypothesis that has been tested, Kruskal-Wallis Test, which is a comparison of the means of the ranked data of the questionnaire:

H₀= There is no awareness on the level of importance of digital marketing strategies across segments.

H₁ = There is an awareness on the level of importance of digital marketing strategies across segments. (Alternate)

Table 6: Kruskal-Wallis Test – Mean Rank amongst Droppers, Gainers and Status quo Income groups, post COVID-19

Summary of Kruskal- Walls – Test Mean Rank by Droppers, Gainers and Status Quo Groups	Drop of income in job or business	No Gain or Drop in Business or job income	Gain of income in job of business	p-value Asympsig (2-tailed)	Null-Hypotheses
Rank, What Digital Marketing strategies required for today’s digital business?					
Social Media Marketing	57.35	67.89	58.67	0.354	Accepted
Influencer Marketing	62.38	63.76	55.50	0.526	Accepted
Live Video Streaming / Video Campaign	59.29	65.60	58.00	0.615	Accepted
Search Engine Marketing	62.42	58.35	59.77	0.854	Accepted
Vlog & Blog Digital Marketing	57.32	63.95	61.83	0.643	Accepted
Digital Marketing Platforms	59.77	60.06	61.79	0.94	Accepted

N = 50 (Drop of income in job or business)

N = 31 (No Gain or Drop in Business or job Income)

N = 39 (Gain of income in job or business)

The three different groups of participants in Table 6. After analysing the p-value > 0.05 in all the above 6 cases as such, the null hypotheses stand retained and cannot be rejected. This also means that there is no significant difference between the ranking given by all the three above groups. As such, there is no difference in the ranking given by the three segments of the participants, Hence Null Hypothesis H_0 stands accepted. The finding from the above analysis is that it further re-emphasizes the point that irrespective of the categories they are all very bullish about the future of the digital businesses in India.

Objective 3: Null Hypothesis 2

The following is the null hypothesis that has been tested, paired sample T Test, which is a comparison of two Ordinal questionnaire based on rating:

H_0 = There is no willingness to give priority to Digital Marketing as a skillset

H_1 = There is a willingness to give priority to Digital Marketing as a skillset (Alternate)

Table 7: Paired Sample T Test 1 – Mean of Digital Marketing skillset & Digital growth %

Summary of Paired Sample Test – 2 Testing the relationship between two ordinal questions	Mean – Rating on Digital Marketing as an important Skillset	Mean – Rating on Profitability growth % of Digital Business post Covit – 19	p-value Asympsig (2-tailed)	Null-Hypotheses
Paired Sample T Test between the Group of Rating on Digital Marketing as an important skillset vs Rating Group on Profitability growth% of Digital Business post Covit -19	2.30	2.21	0.034	Rejected

N = 120 (Total Successful respondents)

Normality test passed with p-value >0.05

Source: Created on IBM SPSS Especially for this Research study

The null hypotheses for the statistical analysis - paired sample T Test, which is a comparison of two Ordinal questionnaire based on rating. In Table 7, the significance value is less than 0.05 and thus, the mean of Digital Marketing at 2.30 is significantly higher than 2.21. Hence, the null hypotheses stand rejected. So, the alternate hypotheses H_1 hold true which is the findings from this statistical analysis are that respondents are willing to acquire digital marketing as an important skillset.

Objective 4: To suggest various strategies for Digital Businesses

Objective 4: Null Hypothesis 1

The following is the null hypothesis that has been tested, using both Spearman’s correlation analysis:

H₀ = There is no correlation amongst Digital Business growth, Digital Marketing and Digital start-up

H₁ = There is a strong correlation amongst Digital Business growth, Digital Marketing and Digital start-up (Alternate)

Table 8: Correlations – Digital Business growth performance, Digital Marketing, Digital Start-up

Correlations				
Spearman's rho		Rating on Growth of profitability of Digital Business post Covid – 19	Rating on Transforming into Digital Business or Digital Startup post Covid -19	Rating on Digital Marketing as an important skillset post Covid – 19
Rating on Growth of profitability of Digital Business post Covid – 19	Correlation coefficient	1.00	.748**	.823**
	Sig. (2 – tailed)		<.001	<.001
Rating on Transforming into Digital Business or Digital Startup post Covid-19	Correlation coefficient	0.748**	1.00	.688**
	Sig. (2 – tailed)	<.001		<.001
Rating on Digital Marketing as an important skillset post Covid – 19	Correlation coefficient	.823**	.688**	1.00
	Sig. (2 – tailed)	<.001	<.001	

** . Correlation is significant at the <0.001 level (2-tailed)
 N =120 in all the cases
 Source: Created on IBM SPSS especially for this Research Study

The correlation analysis using Spearman’s rho (Table 8) a strong correlation amongst Digital Business growth performance, Digital Marketing, transformation to digital business or Digital Start-up based on the responses received. The significance value (p-value <0.001) of less than 0.05. As such the hypotheses (H₀) stands rejected and the alternate hypotheses (H₁) stands true. As such there is a significant correlation of 0.748 at P<0.001 between digital start-up and digital business performance. Also, between, digital marketing skillsets and digital business growth performance, there is a significantly high correlation of 0.823 at P<0.001. Further, there is also a significant correlation between digital marketing skillset and digital start-up of 0.688. Thus, we can conclude that there a strong correlation amongst digital business performance, digital marketing skillsets and digital start-up. Hence, the alternate hypotheses H₁ holds true.

5. Research Contributions & Recommendations

The research contribution and recommendations from this research study has been described in the following points:

5.1. Digital Business is the way forward, huge opportunity for Digital Business in India

The recommendation is to focus on the digital business opportunities, post COVID-19. It is evident that digital businesses are outperforming the non-digital businesses. So, to capitalise on this opportunity and findings from the primary data, the recommendations are firstly, it is important to focus on the digitisation of the he non-digital businesses or traditional businesses. Secondly, opportunities are also there in the fields of Digital businesses like healthcare, banking, and financial solution. Thirdly, New areas like Automated Intelligence (AI) and virtual reality has not been explored much, there is also an opportunity and awareness regarding the same. Finally, Digital Marketing services also comes across in the findings as one of the top digital business opportunities. Figure 2 shows the online questionnaire participants’ feedback about the possible digital business opportunities post COVID-19.

Figure 2: Online questionnaire participants’ feedback – Digital Business Opportunities

(Created using BI Power)

Figure 3: Online questionnaire participants’ feedback – Digital Skillsets

(Created using BI Power)

5.2. Digital skillsets most important skillset for the future digital entrepreneurs

The recommendation is to acquire the digital skills for future digital start-ups and jobs, post COVID-19. Digital skillsets are important to start leveraging that skillset for converting the current traditional business into a Digital business. Following are the recommendations based on the findings from the quantitative analysis of the survey. Firstly, the most popular digital skillset based on the survey is the Digital marketing skillset, efforts must be made to acquire this particularly important skillset in driving the businesses be it current or traditional. Secondly, it is important that trainings and education be given to the youngsters on skillsets of Programming and coding of various computer software languages so that they are better equipped for future. Finally, the skillsets of understanding the overall digital business, which is one of the most popular skillsets based on the survey can be acquired by joining the companies like Facebook, Google, and Amazon to understand their business structure and digital business strategies. Figure 3 provides the feedback by the respondents about the digital skillsets required post COVID-19.

5.3. Digital Marketing is particularly important Strategy and skillset in driving Digital Business in India

The recommendation is that digital marketing training is essential and digital marketing strategy is critical for running any digital business, post COVID-19. The digital marketing comes across as one of the most popular skillsets in the findings as also reflected in the Figure 3, in which digital marketing is one of the most popular skillsets. Following are the recommendations on the digital strategy based on the importance and criticality of this skillset. Firstly, the most critical element on the digital marketing strategy should be that it should be a strategy based on data which can be acquired with access to platforms such as google analytics, this strategy helps in launching a targeted digital marketing campaign. Secondly, Programmatic is another approach to automate the entire digital marketing ecosystem, which is based on the algorithms, this ensures that like AI the targeted users get customised digital marketing campaigns. Finally, for the digital marketing strategy to be successful, it is important that it is implemented with a 360-degree approach and executing all the various elements of digital marketing.

5.4. Recommendation on key strategies for digital businesses, post COVID-19

The recommendations based on the insights and findings on the awareness of various digital businesses, digital skillsets, and future digital opportunities from the primary data as well as the secondary data are as follows; Firstly, one of the key strategies in digital business is having a 360-degree approach to the digital marketing strategy, ensuring the proper execution various strategies like programmatic, influencer marketing, search engine

optimisation etc. Secondly, Social media engagement strategy becomes integral to any digital business, this should have a separate focus along with the digital marketing strategies. Finally, driving innovations and training of future skillsets to be future ready is another important and key strategy for any digital business operation.

6. Limitation and Scope for Future Research and Development

Even though this research study has provided immense insights and has made research contributions, however, it would be fruitful for the future researchers to take this forward from the point where this research had to stop owing to this being a time-bound 23-week cross section study. A longitudinal study in this area would enhance the insights even further and would give us more findings and insights. Secondly, this has been a limited size on-line survey with 120 participants, a bigger participation would capture more insights. Thirdly, focus group can be added for a qualitative methodology into the mix along with quantitative. Finally, with the help of some funding the future research can be conducted in many other cities to get diverse insights.

7. Conclusion

This research study has clearly found with the supporting evidence from the Primary and Secondary data that there is a huge growth opportunity for Digital Business in India, post COVID-19. Digital Business offers a lucrative opportunity, Digital skillsets training is critical for driving the penetration of the digital businesses and Digital Marketing remains a critical digital skillset. To conclude, the research study has achieved its stated objective of examining; Firstly, the new digital business opportunities in India which the findings suggest as Digital Businesses in banking, healthcare being particularly popular with digital marketing services, online digital education, new technologies such as AI and Robotics. Secondly, the analysing of the new digital skillsets has been achieved with the findings that digital marketing is the most in-demand followed by Programming and Coding, AI. Thirdly, the goal to determine the importance of the digital marketing and recommending the strategies has also been achieved with the recommendation of key digital marketing strategies like having a data-based strategy, programmatic – an automated approach to digital marketing and social engagement as one of its key strategies. Further, the objective of suggestion of the key digital business strategies has been recommended with being technologically agile to new technologies such as AR and VR, being data-driven, having a 360-degree approach to digital marketing as a key strategy to achieve its business goals. The conclusions, recommendations are critical for the digital businesses in the post COVID-19 scenario with a key support from Digital Marketing as a key strategy.

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